

STRUCTURE OF BROMO-OXYMETHYLENE-METHYLETHYL KETONE

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The structure of the product of bromination of oxymethylene-methylethyl ketone has been discussed. It appears that the bromine atom in the product, first formed, migrates to methyl side-chain by a rearrangement process.

Oxymethylene-methylethyl ketone (I) was brominated in dry ether, giving rise to a solid product (Agarwal, Gupta and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 55). The bromo compound was given the structure (II).

On further investigation it has been found that the properties of the bromo compound are inconsistent with the above structure. For example, when treated according to K. H. Meyer's process for enol estimation (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2755; 1912, 45, 2843), it takes further bromine; it develops violet colour with ferric chloride solution; it does not undergo inverse substitution on being warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution (a characteristic property of α -halogenated ketones; Bokadia and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 548; Bokadia, *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1953, II Sec., 9) and like an enol it neutralises alkali.

Ethyl acetoacetate by direct bromination (Conrad and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1044) in aqueous medium or by bromination of its copper derivative (Schonbrodt, *Annalen*, 1889, 253, 175) affords ethyl α -bromo-(2-bromo)-acetoacetate (III). When, however, it is treated with bromine in carbon disulphide solution, the product is ethyl γ -bromo-(4-bromo)-acetoacetate (IV) (Conrad and Schmidt, *loc. cit.*). It is also known that (III) is unstable and passes into the more stable isomer (IV) on standing. Bromine in ethyl $\alpha\alpha$ -dibromoacetoacetate (V) also undergoes similar migration (Schonbrodt, *loc. cit.*).

Since migration of bromine in bromo derivatives of ethyl acetoacetate takes place from α to γ position, it is just likely that bromine in bromo-oxymethylene-methylethyl ketone also migrates from α to γ , affording compound (VI), which is capable of further enolisation.

Bromo-oxymethylene-methylethyl ketone on oxidation with Kiliani's dichromate mixture (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3564) furnished a new neutral product, and which by its reactions appeared to be monobromodiacetyl (VII). Its composition has been confirmed by analysis. It also undergoes 'inverse substitution' with acidified potassium iodide, and affords diacetyl (VIII) which has been identified by its disemicarbazone. But this does not prove unequivocally that the bromine migrates to γ -position as this result can as well be interpreted in terms of structure (IX).

A bromine atom attached to carbon, adjacent to the carbonyl group, is endowed with positive character and is capable of undergoing inverse substitution. Several ketones with bromine attached to α , β , or γ -carbon atom with respect to carbonyl group have been examined by the authors (*loc. cit.*). With the exception of bromocamphor (recently examined) all other bromoketones having bromine in the α -position undergo inverse substitution with acidified potassium iodide solution. Under the same experimental conditions bromo-oxymethylene-methylethyl ketone does not undergo inverse substitution. The suggested structure (VI) is inconsistent with the negative results of inverse substitution. A position of bromine, which is consistent with the results of the oxidative fission and also with the results of inverse substitution, is in the side chain of the α -carbon, as shown by the structure (IX).

It is known that when in 1:3-dicarbonyl system containing halogen, the latter being so placed that it precludes formation of an enol, such a halogen is most easily removable

and replaceable by hydrogen to facilitate the formation of enol. For example, when α -chlorobenzoylcamphor, which cannot enolise, is treated with caustic soda, the chlorine is not replaced by hydroxyl group as usual but is replaced by hydrogen to enable the system to form enol of benzoylcamphor (Forster and Micklethwart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 167). Sodium hypochlorite is simultaneously formed. A more striking case is afforded by dibromodimethyldihydroresorcinol prepared by Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1897, 294, 253). He observed that dilute alkali readily removed one bromine atom and substituted one hydrogen atom (not hydroxyl group), but the resulting monobromo compound resisted the action of strong alkali even on prolonged boiling. It seems that sole purpose of alkali is to facilitate the formation of a structure which can produce an enol, and once this structure is produced, further action is resisted. In the case of bromo-oxyethylene-methylethyl ketone, the cause of migration of bromine may be the same, namely to make the blocked system free to enolise.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromohydroxymethylene-methylethyl ketone was prepared as described by Agarwal *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). It has been observed that if more than one molecule of bromine is added, the solid which separates first, disappears giving rise to a yellowish liquid product which decomposes on distillation even under reduced pressure. The liquid product does not produce any colour with ferric chloride solution and does not undergo inverse substitution on warming with acidified potassium iodide solution.

Bromohydroxymethylene-methylethyl ketone is a white solid, m.p. 143° . When warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution it does not liberate iodine. It develops violet colour with ferric chloride, indicating it to be enolic.

The compound (0.1376 g.), when treated according to K.H. Meyer's process for enol estimation, took further bromine, and the iodine liberated at stage 3 due to inverse substitution required 10.9 c.c. of 0.1041 N sodium thiosulphate solution. This gives 73.81% of enol. The compound (0.0314 g.) on its enol estimation by titrimetric method required 10.4 c.c. of 0.1048 N-NaOH, giving its enol content to be nearly 115.5%.

Oxidative Fission of Bromo-oxyethylene-methylethyl Ketone.—To a dichromate-sulphuric acid mixture (11 g. $K_2Cr_2O_7$, 8 c.c. conc. H_2SO_4 and 50 c.c. water) bromo-oxyethylene-methylethyl ketone (solid, m.p. 143° ; 3.6 g.) was added slowly with constant shaking. After keeping it overnight, it was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed twice with little cold dilute caustic soda solution. The neutral and acid components were examined separately.

The ethereal extract containing the neutral product of oxidation after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removing the solvent gave a neutral product, b.p. $90^{\circ}/150$ mm, yield 1 g. It is a colorless mobile liquid. It developed no colour with ferric chloride solution. It underwent inverse substitution. (Found: C, 28.15; H, 3.32; Br, 47.39. Monobromodiacetyl $\cdot C_4H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 29.1; H, 3.03; Br, 48.5%.)

In a quantitative estimation of inverse substitution 0.1287 g. of the neutral compound required 13 c.c. of $N/9.731\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$, which gave nearly two atoms of iodine for one molecule of the neutral bromo compound.

The neutral bromo compound (0.5 g.) was warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution. The liberated iodine was removed by adding just excess of $N/10$ (approx.) sodium thiosulphate solution. It was extracted with ether. To this ethereal solution a saturated solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride in sodium acetate was added. The ether was removed by slight warming and the solution was made homogeneous with a few drops of alcohol. After purification the semicarbazone melted at 277° . Its mixed m.p. with a disemicarbazone of diacetyl did not show any depression.

The alkali extract gave an acid in extremely poor yield, so it could not be identified.

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